

Adaptive data-driven predictive control for MIMO NARX systems: An application to tableting process

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Abstract

This paper considers the problem of designing predictive control laws for nonlinear autoregressive exogenous (NARX) systems based on measured input/output data without explicitly identifying the parameters of the system. First, we consider the nominal (noise-free) case, where we prove the recursive feasibility and stability of the closed-loop system. Then, we explore the case when outputs are corrupted by additive measurement noise. Finally, we discuss the case of capturing the real-time deviations in the system by adapting the data Hankel matrices. In this respect, to guarantee the persistency of excitation condition, we consider three triggering mechanisms, namely, absolute, relative, and mixed. We have illustrated all the discussed cases with examples.

Index Terms

Behavioral systems theory, data-driven predictive control, NARX systems, recursive feasibility, stability

I. Introduction

Due to the advancement of sensor technology and computational tools, data-driven approaches to tackle control problems have recently gained considerable attention from researchers across communities. In data-driven control, system analysis and design problems are tackled directly from measured data without identifying a plant model a-priori. This is particularly advantageous in situations when it is difficult to identify a system model or to derive a system model using first principles. In this paper, we consider the problem of designing data-driven predictive controllers for multi-input, multi-output (MIMO) nonlinear autoregressive exogenous (NARX) systems. It is known that NARX systems are efficient modeling tools and have been applied to model several real-world processes (Billings, 2013).

To tackle the problem of predictive control for MIMO NARX systems, we invoke an extension (Mishra et al., 2021) of a result from the behavioral system theory (Polderman and Willems, 1998) known as the Fundamental Lemma developed by Willems and co-workers (Willems et al., 2005). This seminal result states that every input/output trajectory of a deterministic linear time-invariant (LTI) system can be expressed by a single measured persistently exciting input/output trajectory. This gives rise to a data-driven representation of the model. Note that the Fundamental Lemma holds under the sufficient conditions that the underlying system is controllable, the order of the system is known (or at least an upper bound to the order of the system), and the input component of the measured trajectory is persistently exciting of a sufficiently high order. Recently, necessary and sufficient conditions for the Fundamental Lemma have been derived in (Mishra and Markovsky, 2020), see also (Markovsky and Dörfler, 2022). It is a topical subject to extend this result under weaker assumptions and beyond the deterministic LTI case. For instance, the assumption of controllability has been relaxed in (Mishra et al., 2020); extended to certain classes of deterministic nonlinear systems such as Hammerstein and Wiener systems (Berberich and Allgöwer, 2020), second order Volterra systems (Rueda-Escobedo and Schiffer, 2020), and a special class of NARX systems (Mishra et al., 2021).

Designing controllers for a given system model is well-established in the literature. Topics such as model predictive control (MPC), linear quadratic regulator (LQR), feedback stabilization, observers, etc., can be found, among others, in the textbooks (Polderman and Willems, 1998; Borrelli et al., 2017; Hespanha, 2018). However, designing control laws for an unknown system based on directly measured data is comparatively new. Data-driven output matching problem for LTI systems has been solved in (Markovsky and Rapisarda, 2008). Data-driven stabilizing controllers for LTI systems have been synthesized in (De Persis and Tesi, 2019; van Waarde et al., 2020; Berberich et al., 2020a). Data-driven observers for LTI systems have been designed in (Turan and Ferrari-Trecate, 2021; Mishra et al., 2022). For an overview, we refer to a recent survey (Markovsky and Dörfler, 2021).

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the first paper that uses the Fundamental Lemma to design predictive controllers is (Coulson et al., 2019), where an algorithm known as DeePC (data-enabled predictive control) is developed to solve a predictive control problem based on the measured data. This algorithm is based on the Fundamental Lemma

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and thus does not require an explicit parametric model identification to obtain the desired control laws. Furthermore, because the Fundamental Lemma is concerned with deterministic LTI systems, DeePC is basically developed for the same class of systems. However, it has been shown empirically, without mathematical guarantees, that DeePC also works for simple nonlinear systems with measurement noise by using some regularizers and slack variables (Coulson et al., 2019). The aforementioned work received significant attention from researchers and has been extended in several directions. For example, theoretical guarantees related to recursive feasibility, closed-loop stability, and robustness have been studied for linear systems in (Berberich et al., 2020b) and for nonlinear systems in (Berberich et al., 2022), respectively. An online version of DeePC has been proposed, called ODeePC (Online DeePC), where online measurements are adapted to capture the real-time behavior of time-varying systems (Baros et al., 2022). It has also been extended to stochastic systems by developing appropriate fundamental lemma-like results (Pan et al., 2021; Hiremath et al., 2022).

This paper considers the problem of data-driven predictive control (DPC) for a MIMO NARX system. We use (Mishra et al., 2021) for a data-driven representation of the NARX system. By leveraging the results of (Berberich et al., 2020b), we prove the recursive feasibility and closed-loop stability of the system in the nominal (noise-free) case. In the case of noisy data, we have adapted the setting of (Berberich et al., 2020b, Section IV) and have shown that it is possible to design predictive controllers for NARX systems. We also consider developing predictive controllers when the data Hankel matrices (i.e., the Hankel matrix in (5) multiplying g) are adapted online. This essentially means that we make use of the online measurements to capture the real-time deviations in the process and then modify the control law accordingly. Following the idea of ODeePC (Baros et al., 2022), we remove the oldest input/output pairs and concurrently add the latest (measured) ones in a way that it complies with (5). As pointed out in (Baros et al., 2022), this action might give rise to persistency of excitation condition violation. We address this concern by invoking the ideas from event-triggered control. More understandably, in the instances when the persistency of excitation condition is not satisfied, we deploy and check the effectiveness of three triggering mechanisms: absolute, relative, and mixed (absolute + relative). Thus, the contributions of this work are threefold:

- We design a DPC controller for MIMO NARX systems with and without measurement noise.
- We prove stability and recursive feasibility results for the DPC problem.
- We introduce triggering mechanisms to persistently excite the system.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Prior to formulating the problem in Section III, we define our notation and recall preliminaries in Section II. Section IV investigates the data-driven predictive control (DPC) for MIMO NARX systems in the nominal (noise-free) case, and Section V addresses the noisy case. Section VI considers the adaptive DPC and presents an algorithm for its implementation. We provide experimental and numerical simulations in Section VII. Finally, Section VIII concludes the paper.

II. Notation and Preliminaries

Let \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{R}_{0+} , \mathbb{R}_+ , \mathbb{N} , and \mathbb{N}_+ denote the sets of reals, non-negative reals, positive reals, non-negative integers, and positive integers, respectively. For $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{0+}$, let $\mathbb{N}_I = \mathbb{N} \cap I$. The set of real $p \times q$ matrices is denoted by $\mathbb{R}^{p \times q}$. For a symmetric positive definite matrix $Q > 0$ and a vector x , $\|x\|_Q^2$ denotes the scalar $x^\top Q x$. For any matrix A , A^\top denotes its transpose. If matrices A_1, A_2, \dots, A_r have the same number of columns, we define

$$\text{col}(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_r) := [A_1^\top \quad A_2^\top \quad \dots \quad A_r^\top]^\top.$$

We denote by w_d a typical offline time series defined as

$$w_d := (w_d(1), w_d(2), \dots, w_d(T)) \in (\mathbb{R}^k)^T \quad (1)$$

and call it as historical data. Furthermore, for any trajectory $z : \mathbb{N}_{[a,b]} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$ we use $z|_{[a,b]}$ to denote

$$\text{col}(z(a), z(a+1), \dots, z(b)),$$

where $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$. The i -th power of any vector $z \in \mathbb{R}^k$, denoted as z^i , is defined as the i -th power of each of its components. Following standard practice, if superscript (power) in z^i is left out, it should be understood as 1. We now recall the following definitions.

Definition 1 (Persistency of excitation (PE)): Willems et al. (2005) A k -variate time series $z := (z(1), z(2), \dots, z(T))$ is called persistently exciting of order $L \in \mathbb{N}$ if the Hankel matrix with L -block rows

$$\mathcal{H}_L(z) := \begin{bmatrix} z(1) & z(2) & \dots & z(T-L+1) \\ z(2) & z(3) & \dots & z(T-L+2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ z(L) & z(L+1) & \dots & z(T) \end{bmatrix}$$

is of full row rank, i.e. kL .

Definition 2: A function $\beta : \mathbb{R}_{0+} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{0+}$ is a \mathcal{K} function if it is continuous, strictly increasing and $\beta(0) = 0$, and a \mathcal{K}_∞ function if it is a \mathcal{K} function and $\beta(s) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $s \rightarrow +\infty$. A function $\beta : \mathbb{R}_0^+ \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ is a \mathcal{KL} function if, for each fixed $t \geq 0$, the function $\beta(\cdot, t)$ is a \mathcal{K} function, and for each fixed $s > 0$ the function $\beta(s, \cdot)$ is decreasing and $\beta(s, t) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow 0$.

III. Problem formulation

Consider the following MIMO NARX system

$$y(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{d_1} \sum_{j=0}^{\ell_1} \mathcal{A}_{ij} u^i(t-j) + \sum_{k=1}^{d_2} \sum_{l=1}^{\ell_2} \mathcal{B}_{kl} y^k(t-l), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m}$ and $\mathcal{B}_{kl} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$ are the parameter matrices. Vectors $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are, respectively, the control inputs and the system outputs. For convenience, the above system (2) is rewritten in a more compact form as

$$y(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{d_1} \Gamma_i \eta^i(t) + \sum_{k=1}^{d_2} \Lambda_k \xi^k(t) =: f(\eta(t), \xi(t)), \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \eta^i(t) &= \text{col}(u^i(t), u^i(t-1), \dots, u^i(t-\ell_1)) \\ \xi^k(t) &= \text{col}(y^k(t-1), y^k(t-2), \dots, y^k(t-\ell_2)) \\ \Gamma_i &= [\mathcal{A}_{i0} \quad \mathcal{A}_{i1} \quad \dots \quad \mathcal{A}_{i\ell_1}] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m(\ell_1+1)} \\ \Lambda_k &= [\mathcal{B}_{k1} \quad \mathcal{B}_{k2} \quad \dots \quad \mathcal{B}_{k\ell_2}] \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times m\ell_2}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Systems of the form (2) are known as additive NARX in the literature and have been applied to model several real-world processes Billings (2013). It is shown that system (2) can be equivalently written as (see (Mishra et al., 2021, Theorem 1)):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_L(\eta_d) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\eta_d^2) \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\eta_d^{d_1}) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\xi_d) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\xi_d^2) \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\xi_d^{d_2}) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(y_d) \end{bmatrix} g = \begin{bmatrix} \eta|_{[1,L]} \\ \eta^2|_{[1,L]} \\ \vdots \\ \eta^{d_1}|_{[1,L]} \\ \xi|_{[1,L]} \\ \xi^2|_{[1,L]} \\ \vdots \\ \xi^{d_2}|_{[1,L]} \\ y|_{[1,L]} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

Here, $\eta_d \in (\mathbb{R}^{m(\ell_1+1)})^T$ and $\xi_d \in (\mathbb{R}^{m\ell_2})^T$ are defined similar to w_d (see (1)) based on historical input/output data u_d and y_d . We remark that the single-input, single-output (SISO) case was proven in (Mishra et al., 2021, Theorem 1) and the problem of data-driven simulation was studied therein. The multi-input, multi-output (MIMO) case can be proven in the same way. In this paper, we are interested in synthesizing predictive control laws for NARX system (2) using measured (noisy) input/output data. In the nominal case, we also provide theoretical guarantees related to recursive feasibility and closed-loop stability.

IV. Nominal data-driven predictive control

We remark that the proposed setup is developed for the general case, where the target trajectory could be arbitrary. Nevertheless, and without loss of generality, guarantees of stability are provided for the specific case when the equilibrium is tracked. Furthermore, and for the sake of readability we reformulate system (3) in a state-space representation:

$$\xi(t+1) = F(\xi(t), \eta(t)) \quad (6)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \text{col}(f, y(t-1), \dots, y(t-\ell_2+1), \\ &\quad u(t), u(t-1), \dots, u(t-\ell_1+1)). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Following Coulson et al. (2019), data-driven predictive control problem for NARX system (2) can be posed at every discrete time $t \in \mathbb{N}$ in terms of the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
V_L(\xi(t)) &= \min_{g, \eta, \xi} \sum_{j=1}^L \left(\|\xi_j(t) - r_j(t)\|_Q^2 + \|\eta_j(t)\|_R^2 \right) \\
&\text{s.t. Eq. (5),} & (8a) \\
&\eta_j(t) \in \mathcal{U}, \quad \forall j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, L]} & (8b) \\
&\xi_j(t) \in \mathcal{Y}, \quad \forall j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, L]} & (8c) \\
&\xi_1(t) = \xi(t), & (8d) \\
&\xi_{L+1}(t) \in \mathcal{Y}_f. & (8e)
\end{aligned}$$

Here, $r(\cdot)$ is the given reference trajectory. Matrices $Q > 0$ and $R > 0$ are, respectively, control and output weighting matrices. Sets $\mathcal{U} \subset \mathbb{R}^{m_1}$ and $\mathcal{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^{p_2}$ are the control input and system output constraint sets. The objective, as the cost function shows, is to track a reference signal $r(\cdot)$, which is equivalent to the equilibrium point in case of stabilizing the system (2), and minimize the cost related to control inputs. Constraint (8a) refers to the equivalent representation of system (2). Constraints (8b)-(8c) define constraints on the control inputs and outputs, (8d) defines the initial condition for the system, and (8e) specifies terminal constraints.

A. Recursive feasibility and stability

In this section, we discuss the recursive feasibility and the stability properties of the closed-loop NARX system under the controller defined by (8). Indeed, adding the terminal constraint (8e) allows for guaranteeing stability and recursive feasibility.

Definition 3: The receding horizon optimal control problem (8) is recursive feasible if the existence of a solution at time t implies the existence of a solution at the next time instant $t + 1$.

Definition 4: The output of system (2) is asymptotically stable if there exist a \mathcal{KL} function $\beta(\cdot)$ such that, the solution of (8) satisfies

$$\|\xi(t)\| \leq \beta(\|\xi(0)\|, t), \quad \forall t \in \mathbb{N}.$$

We now introduce the notion of controllable set and determinedness index.

Definition 5 (N-step controllable set): The N-step controllable set $\mathcal{C}_N(S)$ for $N = 1, 2, \dots$ is recursively defined:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{C}_j(S) &= \{\xi \in \mathbb{R}^{p_2} : \exists u \in \mathcal{U}, F(\eta, \xi) \in \mathcal{C}_{j-1}(S)\} \cap \mathcal{Y} \\
\mathcal{C}_0(S) &= S,
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{p_2}$ and $j = 1, \dots, N$.

We denote the maximal controllable set by $\mathcal{C}_\infty(S) = \bigcup_{j=1}^\infty \mathcal{C}_j(S)$. The determinedness index of $\mathcal{C}_\infty(S)$ is then defined as the smallest \bar{j} such that $\mathcal{C}_{\bar{j}+1}(S) = \mathcal{C}_{\bar{j}}(S)$.

The following result gives the recursive feasibility of the optimal control problem (8).

Theorem 1 (Recursive feasibility 1): Assume that problem (8) is feasible at time t . If the prediction horizon L is greater than the determinedness index of $\mathcal{C}_\infty(\mathcal{Y}_f)$, then the problem (8) is recursively feasible.

Proof: Given the feasibility of (8a), suppose that (8) is feasible at some time instant t . The obtained optimal output and input trajectories are then $(\xi_j^*(t))_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, L+1]}}$ and $(\eta_j^*(t))_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, L]}}$, respectively. Since $\xi_{L+1}^*(t) \in \mathcal{Y}_f$, $\xi_1^*(t) \in \mathcal{C}_{L+1}(S) = \mathcal{C}_{\bar{j}}(S)$ and

$$\xi_2^*(t) \in \mathcal{C}_L(S) = \mathcal{C}_{\bar{j}}(S) = \mathcal{C}_{L+1}(S), \tag{10}$$

where \bar{j} is the determinedness index of $\mathcal{C}_\infty(\mathcal{Y}_f)$. As a result and without loss of generality (10) guarantees the feasibility of (8) for the successive output $\xi(t+1) = \xi_2^*(t)$, and thus we conclude the proof. \square

We now provide an alternative condition to verify the recursive feasibility in case the terminal set is a control invariant set. Prior to that, we recall the definition of the control invariant set.

Definition 6: Blanchini (1999) The set \mathcal{Y}_f is said to be a control invariant set for system (6) if for every $\xi \in \mathcal{Y}_f$ there exists $\eta \in \mathcal{U}$ such that $F(\xi, \eta) \in \mathcal{Y}_f$.

Theorem 2 (Recursive feasibility 2): Assume that (5) is feasible and the set \mathcal{Y}_f is a control invariant set. If the problem (8) is feasible at time t_0 , then it is recursively feasible.

Proof: Given that (8a) is feasible, the feasibility of (8) at t_0 yields an optimal output trajectory $(\xi_j^*(t_0))_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, L+1]}}$ and the optimal control input trajectory $(\eta_j^*(t_0))_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1, L]}}$ with $\xi_{L+1}^*(t_0) \in \mathcal{Y}_f$. Since the terminal set \mathcal{Y}_f is a control invariant set, there exists $\eta_{L+1}^*(t_0) \in \mathcal{U}$ such that $F(\xi_{L+1}^*(t_0), \eta_{L+1}^*(t_0)) \in \mathcal{Y}_f$ and thus (8) is feasible with the control sequence $(\eta_j^*(t_0))_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{[2, L+1]}}$. Similarly, the invariance of \mathcal{Y}_f allows us to extend the sequence of control inputs at any time $t > t_0$ using the sequence of control inputs at time $t - 1$ so that the feasibility of (8) is always guaranteed. \square

In what follows, we show that if the terminal set is the origin, stability is also guaranteed.

Theorem 3 (Stability): Given sets \mathcal{Y} and \mathcal{U} containing the origin. Assume that (5) is feasible and the set \mathcal{Y}_f is the origin, i.e., $\mathcal{Y}_f = \{0\}$. If the problem (8) is feasible at time t_0 , then it is recursively feasible and system (2) is asymptotically stable.

Proof: Recursive feasibility of (8) follows from Theorem 2 since the origin $\{0\}$ is indeed a control invariant set. Now, let the optimal output trajectory at time t be $(\xi_j^*(t))_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,L]}}$ and the optimal control input trajectory be $(\eta_j^*(t))_{j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,L]}}$ with $\xi_{L+1}^*(t) \in \mathcal{Y}_f$. Consider the function $V_L(\xi(t))$ defined as in (8) or simplified as:

$$V_L(\xi(t)) = \sum_{j=1}^L \left(\|\xi_j^*(t)\|_Q^2 + \|\eta_j^*(t)\|_R^2 \right).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} V_L(\xi(t)) &= \|\xi_1^*(t)\|_Q^2 + \|\eta_1^*(t)\|_R^2 \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=2}^L \left(\|\xi_j^*(t)\|_Q^2 + \|\eta_j^*(t)\|_R^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

But, since $\xi_{L+1}^*(t) = 0$, then we have

$$V_L(\xi(t+1)) - V_L(\xi(t)) \leq -\|\xi_1^*(t)\|_Q^2 - \|\eta_1^*(t)\|_R^2. \quad (11)$$

Note that $V(\cdot)$ is quadratically upper-bounded, i.e., $V_L(\xi) \leq \bar{c}\|\xi\|$, where constant \bar{c} is computed as in Bemporad et al. (2002) and lower bounded as well $\lambda_{\min}(Q)\|\xi\| \leq V(\xi)$. It follows then from standard Lyapunov theory that $V(\cdot)$ is a Lyapunov function and the equilibrium $\xi = 0$ is asymptotically stable. \square

V. Robust data-driven predictive control

In real-time applications, outputs of the system are subject to measurement noise and thus are inaccurate. Then, the data-dependent Hankel matrix does not span the system's trajectory space, and equation (5) does not precisely represent the system anymore. Therefore, problem (8) needs to be upgraded to account for such an inaccurate prediction. Otherwise, it may be infeasible or lead to system's instability. We consider system (2) with additive output noise for both offline and online data, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}_d(t) &= y_d(t) + \epsilon_d(t) \\ \tilde{y}(t) &= y(t) + \epsilon(t), \end{aligned}$$

where $\|\epsilon_d\| \leq \bar{\epsilon}_d$ and $\|\epsilon\| \leq \bar{\epsilon}$. Then we relax equation (5) to account for the noise by adapting the approach in Berberich et al. (2020b):

$$g = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_L(\eta_d) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\eta_d^2) \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\eta_d^{d_1}) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\tilde{\xi}_d) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\tilde{\xi}_d^2) \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\tilde{\xi}_d^{d_2}) \\ \mathcal{H}_L(\tilde{y}_d) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \eta|_{[1,L]} \\ \eta^2|_{[1,L]} \\ \vdots \\ \eta^{d_1}|_{[1,L]} \\ \tilde{\xi}|_{[1,L]} + \alpha_1 \\ \tilde{\xi}^2|_{[1,L]} + \alpha_2 \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{\xi}^{d_2}|_{[1,L]} + \alpha_{d_2} \\ \tilde{y}|_{[1,L]} + \alpha_L \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where $\tilde{\xi}^k(t) = \text{col}(\tilde{y}^k(t-1), \tilde{y}^k(t-2), \dots, \tilde{y}^k(t-\ell_2))$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,d_2]}$. The optimization problem (8) is then reformulated as

$$\min_{g, \eta, \xi, \alpha} \sum_{j=1}^L \left(\|\tilde{\xi}_j(t) - r_j(t)\|_Q^2 + \|\eta_j(t)\|_R^2 + \lambda_\alpha \|\alpha\|^2 \right) \quad (13a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \text{Eq. (12)}, \quad (13a)$$

$$\eta_j(t) \in \mathcal{U}, \quad \forall j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,L]} \quad (13b)$$

$$\tilde{\xi}_j(t) \in \mathcal{Y}, \quad \forall j \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,L]} \quad (13c)$$

$$\tilde{\xi}_1(t) = \tilde{\xi}(t), \quad (13d)$$

$$\tilde{\xi}_{L+1}(t) \in \mathcal{Y}_f, \quad (13e)$$

$$\|\alpha\| \leq \lambda \bar{\epsilon}, \quad (13f)$$

where parameter $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $\alpha = \text{col}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{d_2}, \alpha_L)$.

In addition to replacing outputs with noisy measurements, we added to problem (13) slack variable α , bounded as in (13f), to account for noise. The theoretical guarantees, similar to the previous section, will be pursued in a future work; however, the effectiveness of the problem (13) is shown in Section VII.

Remark 1: We may need, as in the case of linear regression problems, to add a regularization term to the cost function $\lambda_g \|g\|^2$ with $\lambda_g \in \mathbb{R}_+$ to reduce the complexity of the constraint (12).

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the adaptive data-driven predictive control scheme.

VI. Adaptive DPC and the algorithm

So far, we have not considered changing the data Hankel matrices (i.e., the Hankel matrix in (5) multiplying g) during the online optimization. However, to capture the real-time deviations in the process, it would be required to adapt the data Hankel matrices online. Following the ideas from Baros et al. (2022), we remove the oldest input/output pairs and concurrently add the latest (measured) ones in a way that it complies with (5). However, this action might violate the persistency of excitation condition (also observed in our numerical simulations in the next section). To address this issue, we invoke the ideas from event-triggered control. In the instances when the persistency of excitation condition is not satisfied, we deploy and check the effectiveness of three triggering mechanisms: absolute, relative, and mixed (absolute + relative). In other words, we do not apply the optimal controller computed from (8) or (13) directly, but after using the triggering mechanisms: absolute (14), relative (15), and mixed (16). These triggering mechanisms have been used in the literature to design event-triggered control Borgers and Heemels (2014). Given the optimal control input at time t obtained by solving the problem (8) or (13), $u_0^*(t)$, and the reference signal $r(\cdot)$, the modified control laws are defined, for the absolute, relative, and mixed triggering mechanisms, respectively, as

$$u(t) = u_0^*(t) + \varepsilon_a(t) \quad (14)$$

$$u(t) = u_0^*(t) + \varepsilon_r(t) \|\xi(t-1) - r(t-1)\| \quad (15)$$

$$u(t) = u_0^*(t) + \varepsilon_{mr}(t) \|\xi(t-1) - r(t-1)\| + \varepsilon_{ma}(t), \quad (16)$$

where $\varepsilon_a(t), \varepsilon_r(t), \varepsilon_{mr}(t), \varepsilon_{ma}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $t \in \mathbb{R}_+$, being auxiliary input signals that belong to

$$B_{\delta_i} = \{\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m : \|\varepsilon_i\| \leq \delta_i\}, \quad (17)$$

for some $\delta_i \geq 0$, where $i \in \{a, r, ma, mr\}$. The significance of using these modified control laws is evaluated in Section VII, especially in the presence of model uncertainty.

We perform an initial experiment to collect the data from the system (2) by considering a sequence of inputs u_d of a given length $T \in \mathbb{N}$. The generated sequence of outputs y_d is then recorded. In the noisy case, the outputs are collected in \tilde{y}_d .

Given now the initial collected data reorganized in η_d and ξ_d , the constraint sets \mathcal{U} , \mathcal{Y} , terminal set \mathcal{Y}_f , the reference signal $r(\cdot)$, the design parameters Q , R , prediction horizon L , and integers ℓ_1, ℓ_2, d_1, d_2 , we solve online the receding horizon predictive control problem (8), or (13) in the noisy case with adaptation, as proposed in Algorithm 1, and depicted in Figure 1.

Algorithm 1: Adaptive Data-driven predictive control.

Input: Historical data $\text{col}(u_d, y_d)$, constraint sets \mathcal{U} , \mathcal{Y} , terminal set \mathcal{Y}_f , the reference signal $r(\cdot)$, the design parameters Q , R , integers ℓ_1, ℓ_2, d_1, d_2 , and noise bounds $\bar{\varepsilon}_d, \bar{\varepsilon}$.

- 1: At time t , save the past T measurements u and y (\tilde{y} for the noisy case).
- 2: Solve problem (8) ((13) for the noisy case).
- 3: Apply the input $u(t)$ defined by (14)–(16).
- 4: Increment $t = t + 1$ and return to step 1.

Fig. 2: Schematic of powder compaction process including control and output variables during demonstration experiments.

Note that the parameters in the above algorithm will be chosen based on the problem (8) or (13). Furthermore, at each time $t \geq 0$, the following data are available:

$$\begin{aligned}\eta_d(t) &= \text{col}(u(t-1), \dots, u(t-T)) \\ \xi_d(t) &= \text{col}(y(t-1), \dots, y(t-T)) \quad (\tilde{y} \text{ in noisy case}),\end{aligned}$$

which will be used to update the Hankel matrices of (5), or (12) in the noisy case. In addition, note that a predictive controller, implemented with Algorithm 1, may not track a given reference signal $r(\cdot)$ in case the prediction horizon L is not big enough, or the sets of constraints on the control input \mathcal{U} , on the outputs \mathcal{Y} , or on the terminal outputs \mathcal{Y}_f are too restrictive. Nevertheless, we show the efficiency of our approach in Section VII for the nominal case, the case with noisy measurements, and for system (2) under model uncertainty.

VII. Experimental and illustrative examples

To show the effectiveness of our results, in this section, we consider both multi-input, multi-output linear (MIMO) ARX and NARX systems.

A. Powder compaction process

Powder compaction on a rotary tablet press is a standard method of pharmaceutical technology, which combines several unit operations Brands et al. (2024); Mohan (2012) illustrated in Figure 2. Powder materials are supplied (feeding), homogenized to a pre-blend (blending), and then split-up into sub-units (filling) referred to as tablets by filling into a single die. Hereby, the weight of a tablet y_1 is controlled by the dosing depth u_1 . This parameter defines the position of a lower punch limiting the free volume of the die. Then, pressure is applied to the powder material (compression). Therefore, the die volume is reduced by decreasing the punch distance u_2 between the lower and upper punch as counterparts. This in turn defines the porosity of the tablet y_2 . Finally, the single unit is discharged (ejection).

We perform experiments to collect input/output data, where we manipulate the control inputs (dosing depth and punch distance) and read the corresponding output variables (tablet weight and porosity) via a multitester (ST50, Sotax, Aesch, Switzerland). We note that throughout the experiments, production speed, material composition as well as other process parameters were kept constant. Then we identify the process with system (18), a 2-input, 2-output ARX system.

$$\begin{aligned}y_1(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^2 \alpha_{i1} u(t-i) + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_{j1} y_1(t-j) + \epsilon_1 \\ y_2(t) &= \sum_{k=0}^3 \alpha_{k2} u(t-k) + \sum_{l=1}^3 \beta_{l2} y_2(t-l) + \epsilon_2\end{aligned}\tag{18}$$

with $\alpha_{01} \in \mathcal{P}$, $\alpha_{11} = [-2.7, -2.82]$, $\alpha_{21} = [-8, 4.4]$, $\alpha_{02} = [0.016, 0.073]$, $\alpha_{12} = [-0.0063, -0.0144]$, $\alpha_{22} = [-0.0023, -0.027]$, $\alpha_{32} = [-0.0055, -0.0189]$, $\beta_{11} = 0.077$, $\beta_{21} = 0.137$, $\beta_{31} = -0.006$, $\beta_{12} = 0.294$, $\beta_{22} = 0.27$, and $\beta_{32} = 0.28$.

Fig. 3: Control input and output trajectories for system (18).

We illustrate our results through three case studies with the above systems defined by (18) and (19). In each of the three cases, we generate a set of 150 samples of outputs by considering a uniformly random input time series with zero initial conditions. The observed historical data is thus represented by $(u_d, y_d) = (u|_{[1,150]}, y|_{[1,150]})$ and subsequently η_d and ξ_d are constructed.

1) Nominal case:: Consider $\epsilon = \epsilon_d = 0$ and $\mathcal{P} = \{[49.77, -2.23]\}$. For system (18), we set the reference signal to $r = [250; 0.25]$, $Q = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 10^4 \end{bmatrix}$, $R = 0$, the terminal set as $\mathcal{Y}_f = \{r\}$ and the input/output constraints as $\mathcal{Y} = \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\mathcal{U} = \mathbb{R}^2$. We then consider the problem (8) and compute online the sequence of control inputs $(u(t))_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$ following Algorithm 1 with zero initial conditions. The results are depicted in Figure 3. Since there is no model uncertainty or measurement noises, the output converges to the reference signal and follows it exactly.

2) Case with model uncertainty:: Here, we consider model uncertainty to system (18) and examine the output. The setup is the same as that in the nominal case except that the parameter set is given by $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2\}$, where $p_1 = [49.77, -2.23]$ and $p_2 = [34.84, -1.56]$. We remark that the system operates with parameter p_1 in the time interval $t \in \mathbb{N}_{[1,150]}$ and with parameter p_2 in the time interval $t \in \mathbb{N}_{[151,300]}$. We consider problem (8) and following Algorithm 1, with relative/absolute/mixed triggering mechanisms, we synthesize the control inputs $(u(t))_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$. Figure 4 shows that after a switch occurs in parameter α_{01} , the output deviates from the reference for a short period before being adapted to follow back the reference signal. Note that in case of no triggering, the output y loses track of the reference at $t = 150$ s with a high overshoot of approximately $[2500; 20]$ before tracking the reference again. This results from the fact that at $t = 150$ s, the output is already in a steady state, and thus, the past 150 measurements are almost identical, yielding a loss of persistency of excitation. This is not the case in the relative, absolute, and mixed trigger mechanisms, where the overshoot/undershoot reached only $y = [380; 4]$, $[-200; 0.3]$, $[90; 0.35]$, respectively. The mixed triggering is then a good compromise when comparing the overshoot on both outputs. We also observe, using the absolute and mixed trigger mechanisms, that the output is practically stable around the equilibrium point. This is due to the presence of additive terms $\varepsilon_a(t)$ and $\varepsilon_{ma}(t)$, having a constant maximum magnitude when defining the control inputs. In this experiment, the parameters of the triggering mechanisms are chosen as $\delta_a = \delta_{ma} = 0.1414$ and $\delta_r = \delta_{mr} = 0.0071$.

3) Case with noisy measurements: : In this scenario, we explore the noisy case for system (18). We adapt the setup in Section VII-A1; however, the system's outputs are corrupted by additive measurement noise. We set the bounds on the noise levels as $\bar{\epsilon}_d \leq 0.1$ and $\bar{\epsilon} \leq 0.1$. We synthesize the optimal control inputs online by solving the problem (13). Figure 5 shows the significance of introducing a slack variable to the optimization problem and controlling its value by constraint (13f) as well as the term $\lambda_\alpha \|\alpha\|^2$. By choosing the value of $\lambda_\alpha = 10^{-5}$ and $\lambda = 1$, the output can track the reference with a small error compared to the tracking error corresponding to the measured output \tilde{y} .

B. Nonlinear data-driven control

We also show our results on the single-input, single-output NARX system (19).

$$y(t) = \alpha_1 y(t-1) + \alpha_2 y^2(t-2) + \beta_1 u(t-1) + \beta_2 u(t-2) \quad (19)$$

Fig. 4: Output trajectories (a) with no triggering, (b) with relative triggering, (c) with absolute triggering, and (d) with mixed triggering.

Fig. 5: Measured outputs \tilde{y}_1 , \tilde{y}_2 trajectories and outputs (filtered from noise) trajectories.

with $\alpha_1 = 0.9$, $\alpha_2 = -0.5$, $\beta_1 = 0.588$, and $\beta_2 = -0.24$.

We collect data and control the nonlinear system (19) by running Algorithm 1 as in the nominal case of Section VII-A1. However the objective here is to stabilize the system. Then \mathcal{Y}_f is set to the origin 0, and Figure 6 shows that indeed the system is stabilized for different initial conditions taking values in the interval $[-100, 100]$.

VIII. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the efficiency of data-driven predictive control in stabilizing polynomial NARX systems, both nominally and with measurement noise and model uncertainty, using only input/output data without prior model knowledge. We also enforced the persistence of excitation condition via triggering mechanisms. Future work will explore guaranteeing recursive feasibility and stability in noisy conditions without terminal constraints. Extending

Fig. 6: Control input and output trajectories for system (19).

results to general nonlinear or large-scale systems and finding a lower bound on the time between switching events in model uncertainty cases would also be interesting.

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